

9. SIMPOZIJUM
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ŽIVOTNE SREDINE

ENVIROCHEM2023

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CHEMISTRY AND ENVIRONMENTAL PROTECTION*

ENVIROCHEM2023

KNJIGA IZVODA

4-7. jun 2023. godine, KLADOVO, SRBIJA

KNJIGA IZVODA

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

9. simpozijum
Hemija i zaštita životne sredine
EnviroChem2023
sa međunarodnim učešćem

9th Symposium
Chemistry and Environmental Protection
EnviroChem2023
with international participation

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*This book contains abstracts of
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Wastewater reclamation - risks and opportunities

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One third of the European Union territory suffers from water stress all year round. According to climate change projections and human population increase, the problem will increase across the world in the next decades. Reduced availability of freshwater negatively affects everyday living and economic sectors - in the first place agriculture, tourism, industry, energy and transport [1].

Table 1. Key risk management elements (KRM) organized in four modules for the setup of a risk management plan for water reuse

Module	No KRM	Definition
Water reuse system	KRM 1	System description
	KRM 2	Parties, roles and responsibilities
Risk assessment	KRM 3	Hazards identification
	KRM 4	Populations and environments at risk and exposure routes
	KRM 5	Environmental and health risk assessment
	KRM 6	Additional requirements
	KRM 7	Preventive measures
Monitoring	KRM 8	Quality control systems
	KRM 9	Environmental monitoring system
Management and	KRM 10	Incidents and emergency systems
Communication	KRM 11	Coordination mechanisms

With rising spatial and temporal scarcity of water, municipalities are confronted with the challenge of identifying innovative yet cost-effective solutions to meet rising demands of urban, industrial, and agricultural communities. The sustainable framework for urban local bodies, businesses, and communities is to identify and optimize the nexus between water, energy, and agriculture. Bearing this in mind, the reuse of appropriately treated water from urban wastewater treatment plants (UWWTPs) has been identified as a reliable alternative of water supply for various purposes such as agricultural irrigation or aquifer recharge. However, water-reuse practices are still not systematically implemented in Europe, mainly due to

high governance complexity of related techniques and practices and the lack of social trust. In response, European Parliament has approved the *Regulation 2020/741 on minimum requirements for water reuse* [2] to standardise the legal requirements of wastewater to be considered fit for reuse. In addition, the limited use of reclaimed water is usually related to the risks associated with the pollutants contained in wastewater effluents, especially in developing countries with partially treated or even untreated wastewater. Ensuring safety of the environment and public health when using reclaimed water is essential. It may be achieved with implementing Water Reuse Risk Management Plans (WRRMPs), mandatory for all reclaimed water facilities. To better address and describe the risks associated with reclaimed water use, at European level, the most recent and comprehensive guidance elaborating the 11 key elements of the risk management (KRM) plans has been published (Table 1). Risk management is an essential component of a water reuse system to secure that the reclaimed water is used in a way that ensures the protection of the human and animal

health and of the environment. It is based on the identification of all the risks of a water reuse system and on their minimisation by using preventive measures and appropriate control procedures to timely implement necessary intervention. Figure 1 shows an overview of potential receptors and pathways associated to a water reuse system with different final uses of reclaimed water.

Figure 1. Exposed populations and environments associated to different final uses of reclaimed water (adapted from [3])

This is also expected to transform people's opinions and increasing their awareness of the benefits of reusing water while reducing their biased opinions on using reclaimed water. Sound reclaimed water management is a step forward towards circular economy approach in wastewater management.

References

1. Radini, S., Gonz'alez-Camejo, J., Andreola, C., Eusebi, A.L., Fatone, F. *Journal of Water Process Engineering* 53 (2023) 103690.
2. EU-Regulation 2020/741 on Minimum Requirements for Water Reuse, 2020.
3. JRC, R. Maffettone, B. Gawlik, Technical guidance water reuse risk management for agricultural irrigation schemes in Europe, 2022.

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